

In-situ catalytic upgrading of plastic waste fast pyrolysis oil

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Plastic wastes correspond to 13% of total wastes and only 10% are recycled while the rest are incinerated or landfilled^{1,2}. PET, PE (LDPE/HDPE), PS and PP based products comprise 80% of plastic wastes with high recycling potential towards chemicals and fuels via classical thermochemical and catalytic processes, such as pyrolysis, gasification and hydrothermal liquefaction, as well as novel photocatalytic and electrocatalytic processes³. In this work, the catalytic upgrading of pyrolysis oil via controlled cracking was studied for various pristine plastics (i.e. PE, LDPE, PP, PET, PS) by tuning the acidic and porous properties of zeolitic and aluminosilicate catalysts.

A first screening of the pyrolysis/thermal degradation of plastics was performed via thermogravimetric (TGA) analysis in the temperature range 25-700°C, with heating rate 10°C/min, under N₂ flow 80 ml/min and mass ratio Plastic/Catalyst=4-5/1. The fast pyrolysis experiments were conducted in a fixed bed reactor at 450°C, under N₂ flow 100 ml/min, using Plastic/Catalyst=10/1 mass ratio. The gases were analyzed via GC-FID/TCD, while the pyrolysis oil was dissolved in dichloromethane and analyzed via GC-MS.

In the TGA experiments, the decomposition profiles of the plastics were determined and the main degradation step was within the range of 394-488°C. PET and PS exhibit lower maximum decomposition temperatures (420-440°C) while LDPE, PE and PP slightly higher (454-477°C). Further study on the effect of catalyst properties on the decomposition profiles was performed using LDPE and aluminosilicate catalysts with tuned acidic and porous properties. Using zeolites, the maximum decomposition temperature gradually decreased from 468°C to 391-426°C. The number and the strength of the acid sites, as well the micro/mesoporosity strongly affected the degradation process.

Regarding the pyrolysis of LDPE in the fixed bed reactor, the main products were gases, oil and char/coke. In the non-catalytic (thermal) pyrolysis, a heavy waxy oil (ca. with C atoms >15) was produced (93 wt.%) along with gases (7 wt.%). Using acidic catalysts, a lighter py-oil (with C atoms < 20) was produced (47-59 wt.%) along with less than 10 wt.% heavy wax, while gases were increased to 27-49 wt.%. The main gases identified were propylene, butane and isobutylene. Pyrolysis oil exhibit a wide range of compounds, such as aromatics, PAHs, olefins and paraffins. The catalysts' properties affected both the distribution of products based on their carbon number as well as the type of hydrocarbons. More acidic catalysts increased the formation of aromatics and olefins while catalysts of lower acidity led to enhanced paraffins formation. Furthermore, acidic zeolites also induced cracking and formation of compounds with carbon number C₇-C₁₂ while oxides of lower acidity increased the compounds with C₁₄-C₂₄.

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References

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